

THE USE OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN THE MODERN RUSSIAN LANGUAGE CLASSES AT THE UNIVERSITY

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Abstract: Ensuring the quality of teaching foreign languages to the young generation, fundamentally improving the system of training specialists who can speak foreign languages fluently, training mature personnel who meet world educational standards by mastering foreign languages in our country is one of the goals of the education reform. Identifying opportunities in language teaching and bringing them to life, the teacher's knowledge, creativity, the ability to arouse students' love for their subject, and the establishment of a cooperative relationship with students are the requirements of the current era. The decision to further develop foreign language teaching, implement measures to improve the level and quality of training of qualified teachers who have a high level of foreign language skills for general education schools, vocational colleges and academic lyceums, higher education institutions in accordance with international standards. was adopted in order to provide. At the same time, it should be said that each language being studied has its own rules and secrets. In order to become a mature specialist who meets international standards, the learner is required not to overlook the subtlest layers of the language.

Key words: Russian language teaching methodology, quality of education, interview method, self-assessment method, lecture, interactive methods, abstract thinking.

Educational method is a method of work that the teacher regularly uses with students, which allows students to develop their intellectual abilities and interests, acquire knowledge and skills, and use them in practice. It is a set of regulated methods of organizing the mutual activities of the teacher and the students in order to achieve the specified educational goal.

CONVERSATION method is one of the most effective ways to form a student's personality in an ideological, spiritual, and moral way. When choosing a topic for an interview, it is important that it is appropriate and relevant for the students of this class. The conversation can be organized on the following topics.

1. Ethical topics (social, spiritual, moral, rules of behavior among the community)
2. Aesthetic themes (beauty of nature, human beauty, interpersonal relationships)
3. Political topics (domestic and foreign policy, world events, international relations).
4. Arranging a conversation on subjects related to education and knowledge (the universe and the animal world, etc.) will give a creative result.

During the interview, it is very important to ask students questions that allow them to freely express their opinions and think independently. In this regard, the debate is also very important.

STORY method in which students are usually interested in and love listening to stories enriched with various examples. They can be told about the past of the nation, the lives of fairy-tale heroes, and their bravery. Also, the information in mass media, newspapers, magazines, radio and television will not leave readers indifferent. The choice of the subject of

the conversation or story by the students ensures their meaningful and interesting passage. As a result, students are promoted and ignore the topic. He can express his thoughts freely. This leads to the development of thoughts.

The method of SELF-ASSESSMENT is a type of activity aimed at evaluating one's personality based on the analysis of behavior, qualities, and behavior. Student self-assessment is difficult, but they can be adequately prepared for it. For this, the student should understand his duty, have a reason for education and education, that is, he should want to be educated, strive for self-improvement. This method helps them to assess themselves objectively.

The method of ENCOURAGEMENT is a method of positively evaluating the activity and behavior of students, expressing confidence in it, cheering up and supporting them.

The teacher will have to constantly monitor the changes in his students, be attentive to them. Thinking that they are always in the spotlight, they try to develop and move forward. A teacher should be fair to all students in the community. Then students will respect their teacher, believe that they will evaluate knowledge correctly. This is how teachers find their place in their community.

Below we will talk about new pedagogies that are developing.

1) Artificial intelligence in education. The term "artificial intelligence" (AI) is used to describe computer systems. Artificial intelligence education systems are rapidly entering schools, colleges and universities. While most people think of artificial intelligence as robot teachers, it also has its benefits. Applications designed for students include intelligent learning systems, dialog-based learning systems, inquiry-based learning environments, automatic writing assessments, and conversational agents. Programs for teachers, although less developed, are programs that help teachers improve their knowledge. It is worth noting that the skills of students and teachers such as critical thinking, creativity, communication and cooperation should be taken into account. It would be a great light on light if artificial intelligence were to develop both applications and teaching and learning methods.

2) Learning through open data. More than 250 national, local and municipal governments and organizations worldwide are sharing, creating and using data for their work. These organizations seek to see the data used by the public, and many mature services provide resources for open data exploration. Later initiatives led them to innovative education. So the question is - what does open data offer as material? What is its importance in learning and teaching? The main factor is authenticity. Shared data emerges from real-world processes within large organizations. Information that is often used in professional work has a real impact on our lives and the world around us. The second factor is the importance of data in enhancing students' capacity. This can be a very powerful psychological effect. Students can compare events happening in their cities, villages and even in their classrooms with events happening near and far. Perhaps in the process, they can also identify problems and draw local or community-wide attention to this problem. In one example, high school students in Italy were rewarded for building projects while learning about public funding. It shows that open data has connected readers, and social movements for greater incentives for data literacy, transparency, and evidence-based actions have emerged.

3) Dealing with the ethics of information use. The growing use of digital technologies in education comes with ever-increasing ethical questions. There are many ethical issues here, such as who owns the data, how to interpret the data, and how should the privacy of students and faculty be protected? There have also been cases of criticism of people they are not aware

of. Maybe it's just a matter of time. In order to avoid such problems, educational institutions should develop a policy related to data ethics, obtain consent from students for the use of data, analyze any data from their interactions, and get acquainted with their opinions about the educational management system. The creation of an effective teaching system, as well as issues of student and staff support must also be taken into account. There are currently no formal training sessions. For this, teachers should create opportunities for students. In today's digital world, the mutual exchange of information between institutes and universities will further increase their effectiveness.

What advice do you give your students when they ask how they can improve their Russian? Teachers often advise: listening to a lot of Russian, revising words often, learning the language and understanding how grammar affects meaning. A teacher can help a lot, but not enough time is spent in the classroom for students to really progress; they also need lots of practice outside of school. It is very important for the teacher to look at what the students are doing outside of class and give instructions on how to improve the Russian language. It should go beyond assigning homework and include tools and resources that students can use every day to develop their Russian language skills.

The activity of the teacher is at the center of modern education. The Russian alphabet occupies a central place in the primary education system. As a means of knowing the truth, the Russian language provides not only linguistic knowledge, but also intellectual development of the child, forms the conceptual-categorical apparatus, develops abstract thinking, memory and imagination. In recent years, unfortunately, there has been a sharp decline in the interest of students in Russian language classes, there is no desire to expand children's language skills, improve literacy and speech culture. Nowadays, the most important problem that interests all teachers is to improve the effectiveness of the Russian language lesson as the main form of education and upbringing of students. Lessons held in the same form will tire the student. The monotony of lessons for the student and the teacher reduces the effectiveness of educational activities. Do not force to teach, but arouse interest, it is the duty of the teacher to create a desire for constant learning in the student. A young student has specific age characteristics: unstable attention, predominance of visual-figurative thinking, increased motor activity, desire for game activities, variety of knowledge. All this complicates the teacher's work. In order to keep children's attention during the lesson, it is necessary to organize active and interesting thinking activities. Since traditional educational methods cannot always ensure the assimilation of the material by all students, it is necessary to skillfully organize educational activities in classes. In order to create conditions for the formation of this activity, it is necessary to form knowledge motivation. A creative approach to the preparation and delivery of lessons for teachers can make a positive difference to children. In order to activate students, develop interest, encourage them to acquire knowledge, the teacher should introduce work and other forms of lessons - their interesting varieties into practice, and as a result, create author-non-traditional lessons. A Russian language teacher cannot be guided only by official requirements for the lesson. In order to improve his methodological activity, the teacher should know the traditional and non-traditional forms of Russian language lessons, their typology, and the specific features of lessons in the educational system. Form of organization of education in order to master the studied materials (knowledge, skills, outlook and moral-aesthetic ideas). According to the main didactic purpose, such lessons are divided as follows:

- a lesson to get acquainted with new materials;
- a lesson to consolidate what has been learned;
- the lesson of application of knowledge and skills;
- lesson of generalization and systematization of knowledge;
- knowledge and skills test and correction lesson;
- combined (mixed) lesson.

According to the main method of conducting lessons: conversation, lecture, independent work of students, laboratory and practical work, combining different forms of lessons. The main stages of the educational process are divided as follows:

- Introductory lessons; Preliminary familiarization classes with materials;
- Concepts, laws, rules study lessons;
- Lessons of practical application of knowledge;
- Mixed or combined classes.

Supervision classes serve to form the educational process and its results, the level of mastering the knowledge system (by subject, department, the entire course), students' educational and educational activity skills. Control can be carried out verbally and in writing. Any lesson, traditional or challenging, interesting or boring, has its own structure. The stages of the lesson include the concepts of goals and didactic tasks aimed at the implementation of educational, educational and developmental functions of the lesson. There are different approaches to choosing the main structural elements of the lesson. At the same time, the general didactic structure of the lesson is distinguished by three main (generalized) structural elements: updating previous knowledge and methods of action; formation of new knowledge and methods of action; application of knowledge and formation of skills and abilities. As you know, traditional school lessons include learning new materials, strengthening knowledge, skills and abilities, checking and considering acquired knowledge, analyzing control work, summarizing and systematizing what has been learned, repeating a topic or section. Recently, along with these forms of education, non-traditional or non-standard ones are also widely used.

In many situations around the world, middle and advanced students have access to smartphones that offer a wide variety of apps through helpful app stores. Indeed, there are many of them; Search for "Learn Russian" in the Apple App Store or Google Play and you'll be faced with so many options it's hard to know where to start. One good place is definitely the world-renowned programs developed by the British Council, written by teachers and experts in mobile learning.

In conclusion, these rules and methods are important factors that are needed between a teacher and a student. These methods deepen students' thoughts and help them express their personal thoughts without fear.

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